

Familial Amyloid Polyneuropathy (FAP) – An Overview

Familiäre Amyloid-Polyneuropathie (FAP) – Ein Überblick

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Abstract:

Familial Amyloid Polyneuropathy (FAP), also known as Transthyretin Amyloidosis (ATTR), is a rare autosomal dominant genetic disorder characterized by the accumulation of misfolded transthyretin (TTR) protein, forming amyloid fibrils that deposit in various tissues. This leads to progressive neuropathy and systemic complications affecting multiple organs, including peripheral nerves, the heart, and gastrointestinal systems. The primary mutation causing FAP is in the TTR gene, with common variants like Val30Met leading to the destabilization of the TTR tetramer and aggregation into amyloid fibrils. Early diagnosis and genetic testing play a crucial role in managing the disease, and emerging treatments, including TTR stabilizers and gene silencing therapies, offer promising options for improving patient outcomes.

Keywords: Familial Amyloid Polyneuropathy, Transthyretin Amyloidosis, TTR gene

Zusammenfassung:

Familiäre Amyloid-Polyneuropathie (FAP), auch bekannt als Transthyretin-Amyloidose (ATTR), ist eine seltene autosomal-dominante genetische Störung, die durch die Ansammlung von fehlgefaltetem Transthyretin-Protein (TTR) gekennzeichnet ist, das Amyloidfibrillen bildet, die sich in verschiedenen Geweben ablagern. Dies führt zu fortschreitender Neuropathie und systemischen Komplikationen, die mehrere Organe betreffen, darunter periphere Nerven, das Herz und das Magen-Darm-System. Die primäre Mutation, die FAP verursacht, liegt im TTR-Gen, wobei häufige Varianten wie Val30Met zur Destabilisierung des TTR-Tetramers und zur Aggregation in Amyloidfibrillen führen. Eine frühe Diagnose und genetische Tests spielen eine entscheidende Rolle bei der Behandlung der Krankheit, und neue Behandlungen, darunter TTR-Stabilisatoren und Gen-Silencing-Therapien, bieten vielversprechende Möglichkeiten zur Verbesserung der Patientenergebnisse.

Schlüsselwörter: Familiäre Amyloid-Polyneuropathie, Transthyretin-Amyloidose, TTR-Gen

INTRODUCTION

Familial Amyloid Polyneuropathy (FAP), a form of transthyretin amyloidosis (ATTR), is a hereditary condition marked by the deposition of amyloid fibrils composed of misfolded transthyretin (TTR) protein. The TTR gene, located on chromosome 18, encodes a protein that transports thyroxine and retinol, both crucial for various bodily functions. Mutations in the TTR gene disrupt the stability of the protein, leading to its misfolding and subsequent amyloid fibril formation. These fibrils accumulate in peripheral nerves, the heart, and other organs, causing neuropathy and a range of systemic complications such as autonomic dysfunction and cardiac issues. Though FAP is rare, it is particularly prevalent in endemic regions, with populations in countries like Portugal, Sweden, and Brazil showing higher rates of the disease due to specific genetic mutations like Val30Met. The condition typically presents with progressive sensorimotor polyneuropathy, which often leads to significant disability and a poor prognosis if not diagnosed early. Advances in diagnostic tools, such as genetic testing and biomarkers, have improved early detection, while disease-modifying therapies are emerging to stabilize the misfolded TTR protein and slow disease progression.

DEVELOPMENT

Familial Amyloid Polyneuropathy (FAP) is also known scientifically as Transthyretin Amyloidosis (ATTR). This condition is characterized by the accumulation of amyloid fibrils, primarily composed of misfolded transthyretin (TTR) protein, in various tissues, leading to progressive neuropathy and other systemic complications (Pereira et al., 2022; Luigetti et al., 2020; Schmidt et al., 2018).

FAP is an autosomal dominant hereditary disorder that results from mutations in the TTR gene, leading to the abnormal folding and aggregation of the TTR protein into amyloid fibrils. These fibrils deposit in peripheral nerves, the heart, and other organs, causing a range of symptoms including sensory and motor neuropathy, autonomic dysfunction, and systemic complications (Luigetti et al., 2020; Schmidt et al., 2018; Guimarães-Costa et al., 2019). The disease was first described by neurologist Corino de Andrade in Portugal and has since been recognized in various populations worldwide, particularly in regions such as Scandinavia, Japan, and Brazil (Pereira et al., 2022; Cha et al., 2020; Santos et al., 2016). The clinical manifestations of FAP can vary significantly, with some patients experiencing severe symptoms while others may remain asymptomatic for years (Conceição et al., 2016).

The primary gene associated with Familial Amyloid Polyneuropathy is the transthyretin (TTR) gene, located on chromosome 18 (18p11.1-q12.3). The normal function of the TTR gene is to encode a protein that transports thyroxine and retinol (vitamin A) in the bloodstream (Rajabally et al., 2016; Sekijima, 2015; Sousa, 2022).

Mutations in this gene disrupt the stability of the TTR protein, leading to its misfolding and subsequent amyloid fibril formation (Si & Kim, 2021).

The mutations responsible for FAP are primarily point mutations, which are substitutions of a single nucleotide in the TTR gene. For example, the Val30Met mutation, where valine is replaced by methionine at position 30, is the most common variant associated with the disease, particularly in endemic regions (Sousa, 2022; Santos et al., 2016). These mutations destabilize the tetrameric structure of TTR, causing it to dissociate into monomers that aggregate into amyloid fibrils, which are toxic to tissues (Luigetti et al., 2020; Sekijima, 2015). Other mutations have also been identified, with over 120 variants reported to date (Sekijima, 2015; Pinto et al. (2018).

Familial Amyloid Polyneuropathy follows an autosomal dominant inheritance pattern, meaning that only one copy of the mutated gene from an affected parent can cause the disease in offspring (Rajabally et al., 2016; Sekijima, 2015). This pattern of inheritance results in a significant risk of transmission to subsequent generations, with each child of an affected individual having a 50% chance of inheriting the mutation (Rajabally et al., 2016; Sekijima, 2015).

The incidence of FAP varies significantly by geographic region, with higher prevalence rates reported in specific populations, such as those in Northern Sweden, Portugal, and Brazil. Estimates suggest that the prevalence of FAP may range from 1 in 100,000 to 1 in 250,000 in the general population, but it can be much higher in endemic areas (Schmidt et al., 2018; Cha et al., 2020; Santos et al., 2016). In certain regions, such as Northern Sweden, the prevalence of the Val30Met mutation can be as high as 1 in 1,000 Schmidt et al. (2018) Santos et al., 2016).

The clinical presentation of FAP is highly variable but typically includes progressive sensorimotor polyneuropathy, characterized by sensory disturbances, motor weakness, and autonomic dysfunction (Luigetti et al., 2020; Guimarães-Costa et al., 2019). Patients may experience symptoms such as pain, numbness, tingling in the extremities, orthostatic hypotension, gastrointestinal issues, and cardiac complications (Luigetti et al., 2020; Bolte et al., 2020). The disease often progresses to significant disability, with many patients requiring assistive devices for mobility within a few years of diagnosis (Bolte et al., 2020).

Diagnosis of FAP involves a combination of clinical assessment, family history, and laboratory tests. Key diagnostic methods include genetic testing to identify mutations in the TTR gene, nerve conduction studies to assess the extent of neuropathy, and biopsy of affected tissues to demonstrate amyloid deposits (Guimarães-Costa et al., 2019; Sekijima, 2015). Biomarkers such as serum TTR levels and imaging studies may also aid in diagnosis and monitoring disease progression (Guimarães-Costa et al., 2019; Sekijima, 2015).

Management of FAP includes both pharmacological and non-pharmacological approaches. Disease-modifying treatments such as tafamidis and inotersen have been developed to stabilize the TTR protein and reduce amyloid deposition (Magrinelli et al., 2020; Ishii et al., 2020). Supportive care, including physical therapy, pain management, and treatment of autonomic symptoms, is crucial for improving quality of life (Bolte et al., 2020; Magrinelli et al., 2020). In severe cases, liver transplantation

may be considered, as the liver is the primary source of TTR production (Cha et al., 2020; Santos et al., 2016).

The prognosis for patients with FAP varies widely depending on the specific mutation, age of onset, and timeliness of diagnosis and treatment. Without intervention, the disease can lead to significant morbidity and mortality, with many patients experiencing a decline in functional status within a decade of diagnosis (Bolte et al., 2020; Sekijima, 2015). However, early diagnosis and treatment can significantly improve outcomes and quality of life (Bolte et al., 2020; Magrinelli et al., 2020).

Certain populations are at higher risk for developing FAP, particularly those with a family history of the disease or known TTR mutations. Endemic regions, such as parts of Portugal, Sweden, and Japan, have higher prevalence rates due to the concentration of specific mutations (Sekijima, 2015; Schmidt et al., 2018; Santos et al., 2016). Genetic counseling is recommended for individuals with a family history of FAP to assess their risk and discuss reproductive options (Sekijima, 2015; Sousa, 2022).

Recent advances in research have focused on understanding the molecular mechanisms of TTR misfolding and developing targeted therapies to prevent amyloid formation (Magrinelli et al., 2020; Ishii et al., 2020; Cotrina et al., 2020). New therapeutic agents, including small interfering RNA and stabilizers, are being investigated in clinical trials to improve patient outcomes (Magrinelli et al., 2020; Ishii et al., 2020). Additionally, ongoing studies aim to identify biomarkers for early detection and monitoring of disease progression (Guimarães-Costa et al., 2019; Sekijima, 2015).

The diagnosis of FAP can have significant psychosocial effects on patients and their families. Patients often experience anxiety, depression, and social isolation due to the progressive nature of the disease and its impact on daily functioning (Bolte et al., 2020; Magrinelli et al., 2020). Support groups and counseling services can provide valuable resources for coping with the emotional and social challenges associated with the disease (Bolte et al., 2020; Magrinelli et al., 2020).

Familial Amyloid Polyneuropathy is included in various genetic databases and registries to facilitate research and improve patient care. Organizations such as the Amyloidosis Foundation and the Transthyretin Amyloidosis Outcomes Survey (THAOS) provide resources for patients and healthcare providers (Bolte et al., 2020; Sekijima, 2015). National and international efforts are underway to raise awareness and improve diagnostic and treatment options for FAP (Bolte et al., 2020; Sekijima, 2015).

Numerous scientific studies, clinical guidelines, and support organizations are available for further reading on Familial Amyloid Polyneuropathy. Key resources include the Amyloidosis Foundation, the Transthyretin Amyloidosis Outcomes Survey (THAOS), and various peer-reviewed journals focusing on neurology and genetics (Bolte et al., 2020; Sekijima, 2015).

FINAL WORDS

Familial Amyloid Polyneuropathy (FAP) remains a challenging genetic disorder with significant clinical impact due to its progressive nature and multi-organ involvement.

Although it is rare, the recognition of its genetic basis has paved the way for improved diagnostic approaches, enabling early intervention and better patient outcomes. With advances in genetic testing, biomarkers, and disease-modifying treatments, FAP management is entering a new era of personalized care. However, much remains to be understood about the molecular mechanisms of TTR misfolding, and ongoing research into novel therapeutic strategies, such as gene silencing and stabilizers, offers hope for better outcomes for patients worldwide. It is crucial to continue raising awareness, providing genetic counseling, and supporting research efforts to ultimately improve the lives of those affected by FAP.

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